

Appendix 2.4: Detailed description of population trend of main avian scavenger species in Western, Central and Eastern Europe (data not available in Central Asia). Total number of countries evaluated (Total), number of countries where species' populations are increasing (+), decreasing (-), stable (0), fluctuating (F) or unknown (?). Source: BirdLife International, 2015. NA: data not available (i.e., there are no populations).

Scientific name	Western Europe						Central Europe						Eastern Europe					
	Total	+	-	0	F	?	Total	+	-	0	F	?	Total	+	-	0	F	?
<i>Gypaetus barbatus</i>	7	5	0	1	0	1	4	0	2	1	0	1	4	0	1	2	0	1
<i>Gyps fulvus</i>	5	5	0	0	0	0	8	3	2	1	0	2	5	0	1	1	1	2
<i>Gyps himalayensis</i>	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
<i>Neophron percnopterus</i>	6	2	3	1	0	0	7	0	5	0	0	2	5	0	2	2	0	1
<i>Aegypius monachus</i>	4	4	0	0	0	0	3	0	1	0	1	1	5	0	1	1	1	2
<i>Aquila chrysaetos</i>	16	7	1	7	0	1	18	5	4	6	0	3	7	0	2	1	1	3
<i>Aquila adalberti</i>	2	2	0	0	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
<i>Milvus migrans</i>	13	7	1	3	0	2	15	1	5	4	0	5	7	0	1	1	1	4
<i>Milvus milvus</i>	14	9	4	1	0	0	10	3	1	1	1	4	5	0	0	0	2	3
<i>Buteo buteo</i>	22	6	4	8	1	3	18	1	4	7	0	6	7	0	0	4	1	2
<i>Circus aeruginosus</i>	14	5	3	4	1	1	16	6	1	3	1	5	7	2	0	1	1	3
<i>Corvus corax</i>	21	6	3	9	0	3	19	7	2	3	0	7	7	2	0	1	1	3
<i>Pica pica</i>	19	5	2	8	2	2	19	7	2	4	1	5	7	0	1	1	2	3
<i>Corvus corone</i>	24	6	2	10	0	6	21	5	3	5	0	8	7	0	3	1	0	3
<i>Garrulus glandarius</i>	21	5	1	6	3	6	19	4	1	7	1	6	7	0	0	2	2	3
<i>Larus michahellis</i>	18	7	2	5	2	2	20	5	0	5	4	6	1	0	0	0	0	1